

The History of Emily Montague: the First Canadian Novel?

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Frances Brooke's epistolary novel is by many critics and historians of Canadian literature (Elliott 558, Fraser 1, Hanĵiu 10) considered the first Canadian novel for the simple reason that a great part of the novel's plot (about 70% of it) is set in Quebec. Yet none of the novel's protagonists are Canadians or Canadian settlers or have Canada as their chief object of interest (Their chief object of interest is matrimony and social behaviour.) The present essay argues that though *The History of Emily Montague* displays some interest in Canada and Canada's colonization, the book is not a Canadian novel but an eighteenth-century British novel of manners.

Before proceeding to the discussion of the novel, I'd like to set forth the conditions that, in my opinion, a novel should meet in order to be considered a national (in our case Canadian) novel. A national/ethnic novel in order to be called so, should articulate the specific values and concerns of a national or ethnic community, i.e. its protagonists should be members of the national/ethnic community; its plot should unfold in a particular region (or particular regions) of the country that a national/ethnic community identifies with and claims as its own; while the problems addressed by the plot should be either the specific problems of the national/ethnic community or, if they are problems of a general concern, the way in which they are addressed should shed light on the code of values of a national/ ethnic community.

Frances Brooke's novel falls short of most of the aforementioned requirements for chiefly three reasons: first and foremost because the social-political reality of Canada in the eighteenth century (and the action of *The History of Emily Montague* takes place in the 18th century shortly after the signing of the Treaty of Paris upon which France relinquished its North American possessions to Great Britain) was not propitious for the writing of a national novel. As Arthur Lower pointed it out in his study: *Canadians in the Making: A Social History of Canada*, at that point of Canada's history one could not speak about a Canadian nation or a Canadian national consciousness. The French

colonists¹ in Quebec, very much like the new British settlers, saw themselves primarily as subjects of, and, therefore, felt allegiance to, their respective mother countries. Had Frances Brooke been a colonist, which she was not (Her novel is, at its best, a mock-colonial novel.), for she spent only five years in Canada (between 1863 and 1868) as the wife of a visiting military British chaplain in the conquered French garrison of Quebec, she would still have found difficult to produce a national (i.e. Canadian) novel.

The second reason is Frances Brooke's choice (a very convenient choice, though all too obviously not the right one) to rework in *The History of Emily Montague* the plot of her previous sentimental novel of manners, entitled *The History of Lady Julia Mandeville*. *The History of Lady Julia Mandeville* centers on three couple of lovers: the sentimental Lady Julia Mandeville and the equally sentimental Harry Mandeville, the coquettish and witty Lady Anne Wilmot and the unremarkable Colonel Belleville, and Bell Hastings and Lord Melvin. The characters spend most of their time with pondering their financial situation and analyzing each other's feelings and behaviour or enjoying themselves at rustic parties. The novel has a surprise 'Romeo and Juliet' ending: a misunderstanding ensures that Harry Mandeville does not receive an important letter, which explains how Julia Mandeville is intended for him and has been destined for him since birth. Instead, thinking Julia is to marry Lord Melvin by the design of her father, in a fit of jealousy, he attacks his rival. In self-defense Lord Melvin mortally wounds Harry. Julia cannot tolerate the death of her lover and dies of a broken heart. The other two couples are joined but their unions are tempered by the sorrow evoked by the deaths of their friends.

Just like *The History of Lady Julia Mandeville*, *The History of Emily Montague* focuses on the courtships of three couple of lovers: the sentimental Emily Montague and the equally sentimental Ed. Rivers, the coquettish and witty Arabella Fermor and the commonsensical John Fitzgerald, and innocent but clever Lucy Rivers and the reformed philanderer John Temple. The setting of the novel is Canada (more precisely Quebec) in

¹ "A colony has some aspects of permanence: some of its people have committed themselves and cease to think of themselves primarily as exiles. But a colony draws most of its life from its mother country. It is dependent upon it for most of the necessities of life beyond the simplest, even for food, and particularly for defence and for recruits. Colonials still think of themselves as severed parts of 'the nation', to which they refer lovingly as 'home'." (Lower xvi)

the years just after French Canada had been added to Britain's growing New World empire.

The novel opens with a letter from Ed. Rivers to his friend, John Temple, announcing his intention to become a settler in Canada. The ensuing letters addressed to his sister, Lucy Rivers, and to his friend, are already written from Canada. In these letters Ed. Rivers appears to be enchanted with the awesomeness of the natural scenery and with the exoticism of the natives, but all too soon he loses focus of Canada, because he falls in love with Emily Montague, the apparently orphaned daughter of a British officer and the fiancée of one of Rivers's fellow officer's: Sir George Clayton. Overwhelmed by his love for Emily Montague, Ed. Rivers forgets about his plans of buying land and settling in Canada. He returns to his land-purchasing plans occasionally, whenever he thinks that Emily does not love him. On her turn, Emily Montague hasn't got the least interest in what she calls "the uncultivated wilds of Canada, the seat of barbarism and ignorance" (*The History of Emily Montague*). Her only aim in the novel is to marry the man she loves while maintaining all the outward forms of decorum and feminine propriety. Her friend, Arabella Fermor, the artful and educated coquette, is the most interesting of all the letter-writers and the only character that displays genuine interest in Canada. Her heartfelt, elegant and detailed descriptions of the Canadian winter, of the clothes that they are to wear in order to cope with the cold, of the Canadian winter parties and amusements, as well as the information she collects about agricultural work in Canada and the marriage customs of the "savages" form the lightest and the best-written parts of the novel. Her father, Colonel William Fermor's letters of Canada are of a more sober nature and his interest in Canada's history, the French Canadian colonists and the new government of Quebec is marred only by his much too frequent assertions of British superiority in comparison with everything that is Canadian. At the end of the novel, all the three couples of lovers marry and the two couples that have lived in Canada return to Great Britain.

By choosing to replicate the protagonists and the plot of her previous novel, a novel based in Great Britain, Brooke virtually ruled out the possibility of developing or bringing Canadian-based characters into focus. This is not to say that she entirely ignored them, but that they are never allowed to speak out for themselves and the reader sees

them only through the eyes of the British protagonists. Such being the case, it is but natural that no viewpoint that could be deemed Canadian is present in the novel.

It is true that for a short period of time Ed. Rivers fancies that he would settle in Canada and expresses his “hope to see the *human face divine* multiplying around me; and, in thus cultivating what is in the rudest state of nature, I shall taste one of the greatest of all pleasures, that of creation, and see order and beauty gradually rise from chaos.” (*The History of Emily Montague*). But soon it comes obvious that he is nothing but a mock-settler, a mock-colonist with practically no knowledge of agriculture, let alone the climate of the country in which he wishes to settle: “I have studied the Georgicks (sic!), and am a pretty enough kind of a husbandman as far as theory goes; nay, I am not sure I shall not be, even in practice, the best *gentleman* farmer in the province (*The History of Emily Montague*). As Wayne Fraser pointed it out, “Rivers' reference to the pastoral poem of Virgil seems to be a little joke on Brooke's part: a Latin poem written in 29 B.C. describing agricultural techniques suitable for Italy is a very inadequate manual for "cultivating" the Canadian wilderness” (4). Frances Brooke did not believe in the success of a British settlement in Canada, and one of the characters, Colonel William Fermor, Brooke's mouthpiece in the novel says:

the English are the worst settlers on new lands in the universe. Their attachment to their native country ... is so very strong, that few ... can be prevailed on to leave it The English are also, though industrious, active, and enterprising, ill fitted to bear the hardships, and submit to the wants, which inevitably attend an infant settlement even on the most fruitful lands. (*The History of Emily Montague*)

Colonel Ed. Rivers's half-hearted attempt to settle in Canada², the easiness with which he lets himself dissuaded from it, is a proof in point.

The third reason for which I consider that the novel comes short of being a Canadian novel is the fact that the author uses Canada and its inhabitants: the ‘noblesse’

² “I am at present, my dear Lucy, in the wildest country on earth; I mean of those which are inhabited at all: 'tis for several leagues almost a continual forest, with only a few straggling houses on the river side; 'tis however of not the least consequence to me, all places are equal to me where Emily is not.” (*The History of Emily Montague*)

(the Canadian French seigneurs), the Canadians (Canadian French farmers) and the ‘savages’ (the natives) as a foil to the superiority of the British in terms of liberty³, religion and education⁴ and industry⁵. In this sense the novel is an ode to the virtues of the British.

On the other hand, while *The History of Emily Montague* fails to be a Canadian novel, it is quite successful as an 18th century British novel of manners and, as such, it is a forerunner of the novels of Jane Austen.

According to William Flint Thrall a novel of manners is

a novel, among the dominant forces of which are the social customs, manners, conventions, and habits of a definite social class at a particular time and place. In the true *novel of manners* the social mores of a specific group are defined and described in detail and with great accuracy, and these mores become powerful controls over characters. (324)

The social group on which *The History of Emily Montague* is centered is that of the officers of the occupying British army in Canada and their families. The chief interest of

³ “Dear England! where liberty appears, not as here among these odious savages, wild and ferocious like themselves, but lovely, smiling, led by the hand of the Graces. There is no true freedom any where else.” (*The History of Emily Montague*) (The underlining is mine.)

⁴ Their religion, to which they are extremely bigoted, is another great bar, as well to industry as population: their numerous festivals inure them to idleness; their religious houses rob the state of many subjects who might be highly useful at present, and at the same time retard the increase of the colony. Sloth and superstition equally counterwork providence, and render the bounty of heaven of no effect. I am surprized the French, who generally make their religion subservient to the purposes of policy, do not discourage convents, and lessen the number of festivals, in the colonies, where both are so peculiarly pernicious. However religious prejudice may have been suffered to counterwork policy under a French government, it is scarce to be doubted that this cause of the poverty of Canada will by degrees be removed; that these people, slaves at present to ignorance and superstition, will in time be enlightened by a more liberal education, and gently led by reason to a religion which is not only preferable, as being that of the country to which they are now annexed, but which is so much more calculated to make them happy and prosperous as a people. (*The History of Emily Montague*) (The underlining is mine.)

⁵ The corn here is very good, though not equal to ours; the harvest not half so gay as in England, and for this reason, that the lazy creatures leave the greatest part of their land uncultivated, only sowing as much corn of different sorts as will serve themselves; and being too proud and too idle to work for hire, every family gets in its own harvest, which prevents all that jovial spirit which we find when the reapers work together in large parties. Idleness is the reigning passion here, from the peasant to his lord; the gentlemen never either ride on horseback or walk, but are driven about like women, for they never drive themselves, lolling at their ease in a calache: the peasants, I mean the masters of families, are pretty near as useless as their lords. (*The History of Emily Montague*) (The underlining is mine.)

the protagonists in the novel is matrimony. Throughout the letters, the various writers exchange experiences, opinions, and advice, and in this sense the novel is a critique of love and marriage; examining the importance of "sensibility" in forming happy relationships, and gender relations before, during, and after courtship. The novel is oversaturated with statements and pieces of advice like: "What a charm ... is there in sensibility! 'Tis the magnet which attracts all to itself: virtue may command esteem, understanding and talents admiration, beauty a transient desire; but 'tis sensibility alone which can inspire love." or "coquetry is dangerous to English women, because they have sensibility; it is more suited to the French, who are naturally something of the salamander kind" or "Take care, my Emily; I know the goodness of your heart, but I also know its sensibility; remember that, if your situation requires great circumspection in your behaviour to Sir George, it requires much greater to every other person: it is even more delicate than marriage itself." Or "I love her with a tenderness of which few of my sex are capable: you have often told me, and you were right, that my heart has all the sensibility of woman."

Another thing that the characters are very interested in is the problem of their incomes. It is because of the smallness of his income that Ed. Rivers sets out for Canada – "I cannot live in England on my present income, though it enables me to live *en prince* in Canada" --, and the issue keeps bothering him even after he has returned to England and become a country gentleman settled on a comfortable farm: "Had I my choice, I should wish for a very small addition only to my income, and that for the sake of others, not myself. ... My Emily's suppers are enchanting; but our little income obliges us to have few: if I was rich, this would be my principal extravagance." (*The History of Emily Montague*) Emily's unexpected legacy removes this last obstacle in the way of Ed. Rivers's happiness and the novel closes on a very happy and optimistic note.

To sum up, *The History of Emily Montague* is a skillful combination of an eighteenth century British sentimental novel of manners and a travelogue describing the social, political and geographical conditions to be found in eighteenth-century Quebec under British governance. Such being the case, it is a mistake to regard the novel as the first Canadian novel. Deeming it the first British novel about Canada would be much more appropriate.

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